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The Solution of OQ.I02

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The Solution Of OQ.102¹

In the "Octogon" Vol.5, No.2, Zoltán Blázik, in the open problem OQ.102, asked if there exists a polynomial $P(x,y)$ of at most second degree such that on the set $\{1,2,3\} \times \{1,2,3\}$ it takes the values 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, each of them exactly once. We show that doesn't exist such a polynom. Let $P(x,y)=Ax^2+Bxy+Cy^2+Dx+Ey+F$ be a such polynom. It results that $P(1,1)-2P(1,2)+P(1,3)-2P(2,1)+4P(2,2)-2P(2,3)+P(3,1)-2P(3,2)+P(3,3)=0$. In this sum there are only integer numbers, and each coefficient divided by 3 give one remainder. From this one gets that

$$0 = P(1,1) - 2P(1,2) + P(1,3) - 2P(2,1) + 4P(2,2) - 2P(2,3) + P(3,1) - 2P(3,2) + P(3,3) \equiv P(1,1) + P(1,2) + P(1,3) + P(2,1) + P(2,2) + P(2,3) + P(3,1) + P(3,2) + P(3,3) = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 10 \equiv 46 \pmod{3}$$

and this is a contradiction.

Next we propose the following open question:

Is there a polynomial $P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ of at most degree n such that on the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n, n+1\} \times \{1, 2, \dots, n, n+1\} \times \dots \times \{1, 2, \dots, n, n+1\}$ (the braces are repeated n times) it takes the values $1, 2, 3, \dots, n, \dots, (n+1)^2 - 2, (n+1)^2 - 1, (n+1)^2 + 1$ exactly once?

[“Octogon”, Vol.6, No.1, 81, 1998.]

¹Together with Mihály Bencze and Florin Popovici